

Preparation of Acetonitrile by Acetamide Dehydration over Zeolites[†]

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Synthesis of nitriles involves a vast number of reagents, intermediates and a variety of conditions. Acetonitrile, an important solvent is widely prepared by the following reactions :

The reaction conditions for (3) and (4) are not easily amenable to scale-up.

Zeolites considered as strong acid electrolytes are active catalysts for many reactions¹. The acetamide dehydration considered in the present communication proceed in a simple, well known manner in a continuous production run. There is a

considerable evidence now available regarding the acid sites which are the primary seat of activity. Several different concepts have been used to explain the catalytic properties in relation to the acidity of zeolites. Reviewing the literature on the acid function in zeolites, Rabo and Gajda² explained that differences in O—H acid strength between different zeolites rest on differences in crystal structure and related bond structure. The proton of large T—O—T bond angles and lengths becomes more acidic. In this work acetonitrile preparation by acetamide as precursor is reported in addition to its stand as a model reaction which constitutes efficient means for the characterisation of surface acidity of zeolites.

Results and Discussion

Typical activity data for the conversion of acetamide and selectivity to acetonitrile over zeolites tested are given in Table 1. It can be seen that the selectivity of zeolites tested were found to decrease in the following order at 350° : HZSM-5 > ZnZSM-5 > HM > HY > FeHNaY > NaY. The catalytic picture

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of dehydration of acetamide is that the HZSM-5 zeolite is on the average, the catalyst with strongest acidity. Bond angle in T—(OH)—T strongly influences deprotonation energy. High T—OH—T bond angles tend to increase the acidity. Activity of zeolite catalysts for dehydration correlates with the solid angles. For HZSM-5 and HM, these angles are larger than those in HY which leads to a prediction of higher acid strength. As a result, differences in solid angle H-mordenite displays lower activity than either HZSM-5 or ZnZSM-5. Zeolites in their alkaline form can be used in base-catalysed reactions³. Base-catalysed dehydration reaction over CeX is reported by Rao *et al.*⁵. NaY being basic in nature due to sodium ions, has also shown the formation of acetonitrile considerably less than the other acidic zeolites. The catalysts HZSM-5, ZnZSM-5 and HM can be improved further for a process development of this dehydration reaction as there is no deactivation occurring over these catalysts compared to the HY, NaY and FeHNaY zeolites. In addition, the systems HZSM-5, ZnZSM-5 and HM also can be regenerated back to its original activity after their prolonged use by simple air treatment.

vity has been correlated with the zeolite solid angle which gives the extent of acid strength.

Thus, the test of acetamide over zeolite is interesting from acidity aspect and also very relevant in acetonitrile production in high yields by vapour phase mode of continuous production process. Further aspects of this reaction and comparison with other metal-modified zeolite samples is under investigation.

Experimental

The ZSM-5 (Si/Al=280) and NaM (large pore) were treated with NH_4Cl for 100 percent ion-exchange and activated at 350° for 10 h. The HZSM-5 and HM were characterised by X-ray diffraction and ir methods. NaM, NaY and HY synthetic samples (PQ Corporation, U.S.A.) were used. The preparation of $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{HNaY}$ was reported in an earlier report⁶. The ZnZSM-5 was prepared by ion-exchange method using NaZSM-5 as the starting compound.

The reaction was carried out at 350 and 400° . The amount of catalyst used was 2–4 g. Water was used to dissolve the acetamide compound. The reactant was of analytical grade. A fixed-bed tubular down-flow pyrex reactor fitted with the usual feeding and controlling facilities and operating under normal atmospheric pressure was used to determine the activities of the zeolite catalysts. The reaction mixture was fed from top using sage syringe pump. The product was cooled by ice-cold water using a spiral trap. The product was analysed by gas chromatography using 5% SE-30 column at 80° and confirmed by mass spectra.

TABLE I—CATALYTIC ACTIVITY AND SOLID ANGLE* OF ZEOLITES FOR ACETAMIDE CONVERSION

Catalyst	SiO ₂ / Al ₂ O ₃	Conversion of aceta- mide (%)		Yield of acetonitrile (%)		Solid angle T-(OH)- T	Deactiva- tion
		350°	400°	350°	400°		
HZSM-5	280	90	94	95	90	137–177	No
ZnZSM-5	—	80	88	90	85	137–177	No
HM	10.5	85	90	90	90	143–180	No
HY	5.3	85	90	80	60	138–147	Yes
NaY	5.3	60	70	80	45	130–155	Yes
FeHNaY	—	80	85	70	65	—	Yes

The dehydration of acetamide carried out over HZSM-5, ZnZSM-5, HM, HY, FeHNaY gave 80–90% conversion at 350° and the selectivity to acetonitrile was 70–85%. The selectivity to acetonitrile at 400° was less, side-products and coking being increased over HY and FeHNaY. In case of NaY, the conversion was 80% and the selectivity to nitrile was 60% at 350° . The dehydration acti-

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